

Improved Fusion of Visual Measurements Through Explicit Modeling of Outliers

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Abstract—With the recent proliferation of low-cost, light-weight, and high-resolution cameras, significant research has been conducted on utilizing visual sensors within navigation systems. Visual sensors, however, are different from more traditional sensors utilized within estimation systems because cameras do not directly sense the quantity (or its derivative/integral) to be estimated/fused. Instead, the luminance outputs of the camera sensor are processed algorithmically to obtain some other quantity that is used as an input to an estimator. Sample outputs of vision processing algorithms utilized in automated systems include optical flow, feature tracks, or object localization. Unfortunately, the outputs of these algorithms do not conform to the traditional model of the true measurement plus a Gaussian random process. Instead, each of the algorithms occasionally produce spurious outputs (outliers) that deviate significantly from the true value being observed. In addition, the probability of an outlier occurring and its effects on down-stream algorithms are generally unknown. In this paper, we present an estimation approach that explicitly considers the probability of outliers and performs maximum likelihood estimation over a distribution with outliers. In addition to more accurately estimating the final state, the predicted uncertainty of the system is shown to be accurate.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the recent proliferation of low-cost, light-weight, and high-resolution cameras, significant research has been conducted on utilizing visual sensors to obtain information about the environment within which it is operating. Visual sensors, however, are different from more traditional sensors utilized within automated systems because cameras do not directly sense the quantity (or its derivative/integral) to be observed. Instead, the luminance outputs of the camera sensor are processed algorithmically to obtain some other quantity that is used to represent the environment. Sample outputs of vision processing algorithms utilized for environment understanding include optical flow, feature tracks, and object localization. Unfortunately, the outputs of these algorithms do not conform to the traditional model of the true measurement plus a Gaussian random process. Instead, these algorithms often produce spurious outputs (outliers) that deviate significantly from the true value being observed.

The implications of outliers in visual processing are best illustrated with an example. Let us consider the problem of registering two frames of visual data together using a projective transformation and feature-based methods. This is

a well-studied problem and the details on the typical solution can be found in [1]. When successful, it yields a “mosaic” of two frames which appears to be just one frame. If an erroneous transform was found, however, visual artifacts such as a blurry output frame, discontinuities in the mosaic, or a general mismatch between key features can be observed by the user. Unfortunately, the algorithm performed the same operations in both cases, so the predicted performance will be the same in both cases, despite the dramatic differences in output.

Currently, the presence of outliers in visual processing algorithms is primarily handled through the use of RANSAC [2]. The RANSAC algorithm randomly chooses a minimal set of features and computes a single transform using those features. It then allows all the other features to “vote” on whether the derived transform is valid or not. This process of selecting a minimal set, computing the corresponding transform, and voting on that transform is repeated numerous times. The transform that has the highest number of features voting for it is selected as the output transform. The set of features that voted for that transform are also returned as the set of valid features (inliers).

While this approach yields visually pleasing results the majority of the time, *the ability to utilize the resulting transform in an automated system requires that an accurate estimate of uncertainty be associated with the output transform*. If the derived transform is to be fused with inertial sensor outputs, for example, then an estimate of the transform uncertainty as compared with the inertial uncertainty is required.

One approach for generating the uncertainty estimate of the transform is to assume that all the inliers have Gaussian noise and take the Jacobian of the function mapping the features to the transform. These pieces of information can then be used to generate a Gaussian uncertainty of the transform [1].¹ The problem with this approach lies in the assumption that the set of features selected as inliers is correct. This difficulty has manifested itself in multiple ways in previous computer vision tasks, including:

- If the transform with the largest number of votes still only has “few” votes, the transform is rarely correct. This is currently handled by testing the number of inlier features versus some threshold value and rejecting the transform if that threshold is not met [2].

¹Other approaches are also available for mapping uncertainty from the inlier set to the transform domain, e.g., [3]. These alternate approaches, however, still suffer from the same problems discussed.

- Sometimes, even if a large number of inliers are present, the output still has significant visual artifacts. This has been handled in the past by performing a comparison of “image sharpness” metrics between the mosaiced image and the input images [4]. If the sharpness is significantly different between the mosaic and images, the resulting transform is rejected.

As these prior approaches show, the simple technique of mapping inlier feature variances into the transform domain is insufficient for generating an accurate estimate of uncertainty. To enable the output of RANSAC methods to be utilized in an automated system, new methods must be developed for computing estimates of uncertainty in the output.

In addition to RANSAC-based methods, all visual processing algorithms have the potential for outliers in their outputs. Therefore, the goal of this paper is to investigate novel methods for estimating the uncertainty of visual processing algorithms’ outputs for use in a navigation estimator. Note that the novelty of this approach is not a method to handle outliers better (RANSAC does admirably well) but rather to properly characterize what the effect of the outliers are so that downstream algorithms can more appropriately account for the outliers.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II we discuss previous related work on outlier-aware fusion. In Section III we introduce a modeling approach for outliers and describe how a sequential Bayesian estimation algorithm can be created for this new model. In Section IV we present results of the outlier-aware sequential Bayesian filter on synthetic data. We demonstrate not only improved performance but also accurate estimation of the algorithm’s uncertainty. We discuss further improvements required in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

Within the computer vision community, the presence of outliers within visual measurements is a well-established fact, making the handling of outliers a significant topic of research over the past few decades. There have been three basic techniques developed for rejecting outliers: (1) threshold testing, (2) RANSAC-based techniques, and (3) alternative estimators. We discuss each of these below.

A. Threshold Utilization

In situations where outliers are not overly common, threshold-based techniques can be used to reject outliers. This approach is particularly common in the Visual SLAM context [5], [6] where statistical gating is used to reject features whose location does not comport with its prior model. Similarly, in [7] a least squares model explaining all input data is used to find outliers that do not comport with the model. After classifying these features as outliers, a least squares solution is recomputed without the outliers. These iterations continue until convergence. In [4], a method for rejecting image registrations that do not meet a similarity threshold in focus metrics is described. The weaknesses of these approaches are described at the end of the following sub-section.

B. RANSAC-based Techniques

The development of the RANSAC algorithm [2] represented a significant breakthrough in computer vision as RANSAC is able to find the most likely output in the case of significant outliers in the data. Most previous techniques depended on the percentage of outliers being a minor portion of the data. RANSAC, on the other hand, is able to handle outlier probabilities larger than 50%. Later improvements were made to enable more rapid convergence [8], [9], convergence to a more accurate estimate [10], [11], handling of heteroscedastic noise [12], and integrating statistical sampling techniques with RANSAC [10], [13] to increase the probability of finding the correct output.

One of the weaknesses of both RANSAC-based methods and thresholding is that the proper threshold for rejection has to be selected. As with any thresholding problem, choosing the correct threshold is a trade-off between the quantity of false positives and false negatives. In addition, the binary (accept/reject) nature of thresholds is suboptimal when values close to the threshold are considered as minute differences in their values can cause dramatically different estimates. Therefore, many computer vision techniques now use RANSAC-based techniques to compute an initial estimate, followed by an alternative estimator to refine that solution.

C. Alternative Estimators

In [14], a mean shift based algorithm [15] is proposed that demonstrates improved results over RANSAC. In statistics, the area of *Robust Statistics* [16] has also received significant attention. In general, the concept behind robust statistics is to make statistical algorithms more robust to deviances from the expected probability distributions. This is generally achieved through the use of *influence functions* that bound the effect that any one measurement can have on the final result. Compared with the thresholding techniques described before, influence functions have the advantage of gracefully transitioning from the inlier to outlier state. On the other hand, the influence functions only down-weights the correct measurements as outliers if a relatively accurate starting estimate is already known. Because of this accuracy requirement, influence functions have primarily been used in the final step of computer vision algorithms. In particular, bundle adjustment [17] makes use of influence functions to increase robustness to outliers.

As shown, there has been a significant amount of research performed on rejecting outliers. The focus of this past research, however, has primarily focused on finding the best output measurement rather than accurately modeling the uncertainty in that output. As described in Section I, if the outputs are to be fused with other measurements in an estimation system, an accurate representation of the output’s uncertainty is as critical as an accurate estimate. Generating an accurate uncertainty estimate for visual processing algorithms is the focus of this paper.

III. OUTLIER-AWARE FILTERING

To enable a filtering approach similar to the Kalman filter, we first propose a probability model – the *Convex Combination*

Model (CCM) – that explicitly assumes the presence of outliers. This model is formed using a convex combination (all weights are ≥ 0 and sum to 1) of inlier and outlier probability distributions, where the probability distribution for an inlier is a Gaussian distribution ($\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$) with mean μ and covariance Σ . To model the outliers, we assume a uniform distribution over some space of size V , leading to a probability of $\frac{1}{V}$. Note that because the model is a convex combination of valid probability distributions, the output is also a valid probability distribution (the model is never negative and it integrates to 1.) We assume that the probability of an outlier occurring is α . Therefore, the total probability distribution for an individual measurement can be represented as

$$(1 - \alpha)\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma) + \alpha \frac{1}{V}. \quad (1)$$

Note that we are generally assuming that $V \gg |\Sigma|$ where $|\Sigma|$ is the determinant of Σ . As filtering occurs, there will be multiple different candidate inlier distributions, leading to the distribution

$$\alpha \frac{1}{V} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{in}} k_i \mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \Sigma_i), \quad (2)$$

where $1 - \alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{in}} k_i$, N_{in} is the number of candidate inlier distributions, $\alpha \geq 0$, and $\{k_i \geq 0 : \forall k_i\}$. Because each of the individual distributions are a valid probability distribution and this is a convex combination of distributions, the output is also a valid probability distribution.

With this basic probability model, we would like to create a sequential Bayesian filter that explicitly considers outliers. Therefore, we require an update (measurement) step, a prediction step, and to maintain computationally feasibility, a trimming step. Each of these is described in the following subsections.

A. The Measurement Step

To enable sequential Bayesian filtering, one of the primary operations to be performed is the multiplication of two probability distributions. Assuming two distributions modeled as shown in Equation (1) and their product P_n , we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} P_n(x) &= \left(\frac{\beta_1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}} |\Sigma_1|^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(x-\mu_1)^\top \Sigma_1^{-1}(x-\mu_1)} + \alpha_1 \frac{1}{V} \right) \\ &\quad \left(\frac{\beta_2}{(2\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}} |\Sigma_2|^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(x-\mu_2)^\top \Sigma_2^{-1}(x-\mu_2)} + \alpha_2 \frac{1}{V} \right) \\ &= \gamma \frac{\beta_1 \beta_2}{(2\pi)^d \sqrt{|\Sigma_1| |\Sigma_2|}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(x-\mu_n)^\top \Sigma_n^{-1}(x-\mu_n)} + \\ &\quad \beta_1 \alpha_2 \frac{1}{V} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}} |\Sigma_1|^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(x-\mu_1)^\top \Sigma_1^{-1}(x-\mu_1)} + \quad (3) \\ &\quad \beta_2 \alpha_1 \frac{1}{V} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}} |\Sigma_2|^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(x-\mu_2)^\top \Sigma_2^{-1}(x-\mu_2)} + \\ &\quad \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \frac{1}{V^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\beta = 1 - \alpha$, d is the dimension of the space in which the probability functions lie, $\Sigma_n^{-1} = \Sigma_1^{-1} + \Sigma_2^{-1}$, and $\mu_n = \Sigma_n(\Sigma_1^{-1}\mu_1 + \Sigma_2^{-1}\mu_2)$ (the traditional output result of

multiplying two Gaussians together. Also, γ is a scalar used to complete the square when multiplying the two Gaussian distributions and is defined as:

$$\gamma = e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mu_1^\top \Sigma_1^{-1} \mu_1 + \mu_2^\top \Sigma_2^{-1} \mu_2 - (\Sigma_1^{-1} \mu_1 + \Sigma_2^{-1} \mu_2)^\top \Sigma_n (\Sigma_1^{-1} \mu_1 + \Sigma_2^{-1} \mu_2)}$$

Note that for $P_n(x)$ to be a valid probability distribution, it should integrate to one. This requires multiplication by a global scale factor

$$k = \frac{1}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P_n(x) dx}. \quad (4)$$

The integral of $P_n(x)$ can be expressed as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P_n(x) dx = \frac{\beta_1 \beta_2 \gamma \sqrt{(2\pi)^d |\Sigma_n|}}{(2\pi)^d \sqrt{|\Sigma_1| |\Sigma_2|}} + \frac{\beta_1 \alpha_2}{V} + \frac{\beta_2 \alpha_1}{V} + \frac{\alpha_1 \alpha_2}{V} \quad (5)$$

Note that this equation illuminates several important results of multiplying two convex combination probability distributions together. Because γ varies from 0 to 1, with it achieving 1 when $\mu_1 = \mu_2$, the closer together the two means of the Gaussian distributions are, the larger their weight is in the new probability distribution. In other words, the probability of the current state being an outlier is lower the closer the means of the Gaussian distributions. Second, because all terms that included an outlier are divided by V , the relative probability of the output being an outlier only becomes significant as γ decreases.

B. The Prediction Step

With the Kalman filter, the prediction step consists of essentially two steps: (1) a propagation of the current state forward in time and (2) a summation of two random variables. In essence, this is the same process followed for the prediction step of this outlier-aware filtering method, except that the simple Kalman filter process has to be repeated for every combination of the current state and the input variables, with the following rules:

- The combination of two outlier distributions leads to an outlier distribution.
- The combination of an outlier and inlier distribution is still an outlier distribution.
- The combination of two inlier distributions is handled like the typical combination of random variables used in the Kalman Filter.

For example, if you have an input distribution P_x that is being updated by the linear function F , plus there are some inputs u with distribution P_u , you obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} P_x &= \alpha_x \frac{1}{V} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_x} k_{i,x} \mathcal{N}(\mu_{i,x}, \Sigma_{i,x}) \\ P_u &= \alpha_u \frac{1}{V} + \sum_{j=1}^{N_u} k_{j,u} \mathcal{N}(\mu_{j,u}, \Sigma_{j,u}) \\ P_n &= (\alpha_x + (1 - \alpha_x) \alpha_u) \frac{1}{V} \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{N_x} \sum_{j=1}^{N_u} k_{i,x} k_{j,u} \mathcal{N}(F\mu_{i,x} + \mu_{j,u}, F\Sigma_{i,x}F^\top + \Sigma_{j,u}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

TABLE I

THIS TABLE PRESENTS THE SIMULATION PARAMETERS FOR EXAMPLE SCENARIO USED TO GENERATE FIGURE 1.

Parameter	Value
Frame-to-frame Noise ($\sqrt{\Sigma_u}$)	0.2
Frame-to-frame Outlier Probability (α_u)	0.05
Measurement noise ($\sqrt{\Sigma_z}$)	0.1
Measurement Outlier Probability (α_z)	0.5
Area of outliers (V)	1000000

Because both input distributions are convex combinations of valid probability distributions, by enumerating all possible combinations, the output will also be a valid, convex sum of probability distributions.

C. Trimming the Distributions

Note that in both the prediction and update step, the number of probability distributions joining the convex combination increases to almost $N_a \cdot N_b$ after each step. To enable computationally feasible filtering, an trimming the size of the convex combination is necessary. Otherwise, the number of probability distributions will grow exponentially. Currently, this trimming is performed by removing low-weighted distributions (i.e., distribution has a convex weight of less than 0.1%) and adding their weight to the outlier distribution. Note that it may be possible to more intelligently prune distributions when there are two distributions with essentially the same mean, for example. However, these methods are not trivial. For now the simple low-weight trimming algorithm is used with sufficiently accurate results.

With these basic steps, a sequential Bayesian filter can be designed that explicitly models outliers, their probability of occurrence, and their effect on the estimated uncertainty of the filter output.

IV. RESULTS

To understand the impact of filtering with explicit outlier modeling, we created a simple scenario that models the 2-D location of an object being computed using image-based techniques. During the prediction step, frame-to-frame translation is estimated, leading to a 2-D shift in the current position. During the update step, the location of the camera is computed relative to a global image. Because both the prediction and update steps are modeling image processing algorithms, all measurements have an associated probability of being an outlier. The parameters associated with this simulation are shown in Table I.

In Figure 1, we present comparative results between a Bayesian filter using the convex combination of distributions with a traditional Kalman filter with statistical gating. In Figure 1(a), we show the result of sequential Bayesian filtering with the convex combination of distributions. The plot consists of the “truth line” (the yellow diagonal line), and the highest-weighted of the convex combination of distributions at each time step. The highest-weighted distribution is displayed as a circle centered at the mean of the distribution, the radius of the

circle is three times the standard deviation of the distribution (all noise is isotropic) and the darker the circle, the closer the convex weight is to 1. Note that at two points in the graph, outliers in the prediction measurements cause an outlier distribution to be the highest weighted distribution. This error is quickly remedied, however, and the resulting estimates are still accurate. Most important, the weighting assigned to the outlier measurement decreases rapidly when the results are not close to the truth.

For comparison, we also implemented a Kalman filter with statistical gating in the measurement step, with results shown in Figure 1(b). In essence, if the measurement update exceeded a chi-squared test of probability, it was rejected. The green circles in this graph are the results of the gated Kalman filter, with all other data on the graph the same as for Figure 1(a). While it appropriately handles outliers in the measurement step, it cannot handle the situation of outliers in the prediction step. Also note that the outputs of the Kalman filter show 3 significant jumps due to prediction step outliers, while only two significant jumps occurred with the convex combination approach.

A. Proper modeling of outlier uncertainty

While improving the accuracy of the filter output is important, just as important is the ability to accurately predict the uncertainty associated with that output. With Kalman filtering, this information is provided as a covariance matrix that describes the accuracy associated with each variable in the state vector and their inter-relationships. With the CCM introduced in this paper, a list of weights for different distributions, together with a mean and covariance for each distribution is returned – plus a probability that the output is an outlier. It is important to know how correct these estimates of uncertainty are in the presence of outliers.

To measure how accurately the current approach estimates the uncertainty of the output results, we ran the previous simulation for 10,000 time steps. This gives us 10,000 samples of the “truth” that can be used to compare against the predicted distributions. Unfortunately, this sampled version of the truth means that prior tools for comparing probability distributions were not applicable to this scenario. Typical tools used for comparing probability distributions are described in Table II, together with a brief explanation of why that method could not be used in this case.

To enable comparison of the observed and predicted probability distribution, a discrete version of entropy was used. A 50x50 sized area around the true location at each time step was divided in 0.05x0.05 blocks, for a total of one million blocks. Using the predicted probability distribution, the probability of each block having the true location was computed. From this, the total entropy of the predicted distribution was computed as

$$- \sum_{i=1}^{1000000} p_i \log_2 p_i, \quad (7)$$

where p_i is the probability of the true value being in block i computed from the predicted distribution. Similarly, the true entropy for that time step is computed as $-p_t \log_2 p_t$, where

Fig. 1. This figure presents comparative results between a statistical gating and convex combination-based filtering method for handling outliers. Note that not only are the convex combination results more accurate, but the convex combinations routine provides useful feedback on the certainty of the displayed results (darker circles=more certain results).

TABLE II

THIS TABLE PRESENTS A SUMMARY OF POSSIBLE METHODS FOR EVALUATING THE ACCURACY OF PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTIONS AND THEIR SHORTCOMINGS FOR OUTLIER-AWARE FILTERING EVALUATION.

Method	Mismatch to current scenario
NEES (Normalized Estimation Error Squared)	While simple to compute, the NEES metric assumes the predicted probability distribution is Gaussian. It is not easily extended to a convex combination of Gaussians.
Kullback-Leibler Divergence	While this metric can be used with any two probability distributions, the “true” distribution changes between each time stamp. Despite this change, we are only obtaining one sample at each time step. This makes it impossible to use the Kullback-Leibler divergence to compare the truth distribution with the estimated distributions in our scenario.
Continuous Entropy of Gaussian Distributions	While a “continuous” entropy can be computed for Gaussian Distributions, you cannot compare continuous and discrete entropy estimates. Therefore, a sampled truth value cannot be numerically compared against the continuous estimate of the distribution.

TABLE III

THIS TABLE PRESENTS RESULTS QUANTIFYING THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE PREDICTED AND ACTUAL ENTROPY VALUES FOR BOTH THE STATISTICAL GATING AND CCM METHODS FOR HANDLING OUTLIERS. AS SHOWN, THE CCM METHOD MUCH MORE ACCURATELY PREDICTS THE UNCERTAINTY OF ITS ESTIMATES.

Statistical Gating	Entropy Value
Observed (truth)	100*
Predicted	9.72
CCM	
Observed (truth)	8.63
Predicted	8.76
*Some entries were so improbable that they required infinite entropy. Instead, a threshold of 199 bits was used for every entry higher than the threshold.	

t is the grid square that has the true location in it. Over the 10,000 time steps, the average observed and estimated entropy was computed, with the results shown in Table III. Note that the entropy from the statistical gating is off by over an order of

magnitude, while the difference between the true and predicted entropy for the CCM is only 1.5%. This demonstrates that using the CCM filtering algorithm not only improves the performance of the filter, but also enables accurate uncertainty estimates to be generated by the algorithm.

V. CONCLUSION/FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have discussed the need for outlier-aware filtering algorithms. A proposed approach, the convex combination model (CCM) is presented for explicitly considering outliers in the filtering algorithm. The necessary prediction, update, and trimming steps are derived for this model, and significant gains in performance and uncertainty estimates are achieved. Future work in this area is needed to (a) verify the improved performance of this filtering algorithm with real data, (b) collect enough real data that the uncertainty estimates of an outlier-aware filter can be verified, and (c) create methods for estimating the probability of an outlier that

are not application and scenario dependent. Pursuing each of these efforts is the subject of future research.

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